
Position: Cross-Layer Co-Design Is Necessary to Safely Deploy Agentic AI in Real-Time Systems

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Abstract

This *position paper* argues that the rapid advancement of Generative AI (GenAI), driving the emergence of reasoning capabilities in Large Language Models (LLMs), is creating a paradigm shift in autonomous cyber-physical systems where AI-based agentic models are integrated into real-time decision making. Concurrently, the demand for real-time (RT) computing and connectivity in industrial, automotive, and robotic applications remains critical.

We argue that the inevitable convergence of these two domains exposes a fundamental mismatch between probabilistic agentic AI workloads and deterministic real-time requirements. We delineate two primary modes of convergence: the isolation of resource-intensive agentic workloads from RT tasks that need deterministic execution on shared platforms, and the direct integration of agentic AI into time-sensitive decision making within cyber-physical systems. For each mode, we identify key applications, outline fundamental challenges such as resource contention and temporal unpredictability, and survey state-of-the-art solutions spanning compute platforms, communication stacks, and application-level strategies. We conclude that future progress requires a cross-layer co-design approach, encompassing new system-level timing models, real-time agentic frameworks, and novel certification methodologies, to bridge the gap between the probabilistic nature of GenAI and the deterministic needs of real-time workloads.

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1. Introduction: Agentic AI and Real-Time Workloads

1.1. The Convergence of Agentic AI and Real-Time Workloads

A significant technological shift is underway, where agentic AI is reaching human or super-human levels of performance at multiple cognitive tasks. These new capabilities are enabling novel automation solutions in many vertical domains, including cyber-physical systems that require decision making in real-time, which in many cases translates to deterministic task execution or task execution with very low latency and jitter.

Early autonomous cyber-physical systems were dominated by rule-based, deterministic expert systems, which were highly predictable yet functionally limited in their ability to handle unforeseen scenarios (Shortliffe & Buchanan, 1975). The subsequent era saw the rise of discriminative AI, including deep neural networks for perception (Krizhevsky et al., 2017) and reinforcement learning for control (Mnih et al., 2015; Sutton et al., 1999). These models introduced probabilistic learning but largely maintained deterministic execution paths and predictable computational graphs once trained, allowing for a degree of temporal analysis. In both rule- and discriminative AI-based systems, the main challenge for deterministic execution time resides on the underlying compute platform, where performance optimization decisions may tradeoff timing guarantees.

The present and future, however, are characterized by Generative AI-based *agentic* systems.

Embedding agentic AI in cyber-physical systems is enabling unprecedented levels of embodied cognition, where machines can perceive their environment, reason about complex situations, and execute actions that interact with the physical world.

These systems leverage Large Language Models (LLMs) (Vaswani et al., 2017), and other multi-modal variations such as Vision-Language-Action models (VLAs), for complex cognitive tasks such as autonomous planning (Yao et al., 2023), dynamic tool use (Schick et al., 2023), and integrated learning. However, in contrast to discriminative AI,

generative AI-based systems exhibit inherently probabilistic response delays. This uncertainty stems from multiple sources: a) the auto-regressive nature of LLMs produces results sequentially with a probabilistic inference delay; b) agentic systems use LLMs to generate execution plans which have no formal latency bound guarantees; and c) these agents orchestrate complex flows involving data gathering, tool execution, and communication, each introducing its own variable latency.

Thus, although much more capable, it is much more challenging to integrate generative AI-based agentic solutions into cyber-physical systems that must interact with the physical world in real-time and meet strict deterministic timing requirements. This contrast is illustrated in Fig. 1, which highlights the temporal predictability gap between deterministic RT workloads and probabilistic agentic AI workloads, as well as the two convergence directions explored in this paper.

Figure 1. Conceptual contrast between deterministic real-time (RT) workloads and probabilistic agentic AI workloads, highlighting the temporal predictability gap and two convergence directions explored in this paper.

In this paper, we analyze two distinct ways in which agentic AI will converge with RT cyber-physical systems:

- **Isolation:** Deploying agentic AI workloads alongside traditional (model-based) RT workloads on shared hardware, where the primary goal is to shield the timing guarantees of RT decision-making from AI-induced interference.
- **Integration:** Enabling the direct use of agentic AI within real-time decision making loops that have their own timing constraints, requiring the AI’s response time itself must be bounded and predictable.

We argue that without explicit time-aware abstractions and contracts spanning the entire agentic stack, agentic AI cannot be safely and scalably deployed beyond isolated roles in real-time cyber-physical systems, and that future progress therefore requires a cross-layer co-design approach to bridge the gap between the probabilistic nature of GenAI and the deterministic needs of real-time workloads.

1.2. An Overview of Agentic AI

The engine of modern agentic AI are Large Language Models (Vaswani et al., 2017; bro), most commonly built on the Transformer architecture. These models operate auto-regressively, analyzing all input text at once through multiple attention layers, and generating an output sequence one token at a time until a stop condition is met. While their scale enables emergent reasoning and planning capabilities, it also imposes immense computational and memory demands. Current state-of-the-art LLMs have billions of parameters that only high performance computers can serve. To democratize this technology, Small Language Models (SLMs) have gained prominence as down-sized versions that seek to retain performance at a much lower cost. While a foundational, or commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) LLM can be readily deployed to a vast number of vertical domains, a SLM needs a significant adaptation effort to achieve a competitive performance.

LLMs/SLMs are the key ingredient in agentic AI systems but they are not the only component. The architecture of agentic systems is inherently complex and multi-layered, spanning from the application-level guardrails and orchestration layers down to the agent flow, context management, and neural network layers, all resting upon the physical hardware (Liang, 2025). This layered complexity is a primary source of test-time computational uncertainty (Liang, 2025). The latency of an agent’s response is subject to three main variables:

First, the LLM/SLM latency, dominated by the probabilistic length of the LLM/SLM generated output (i.e., number of generated tokens), which is non-deterministic even under controlled settings (Machines, 2026). The serving latency of each produced token is determined by the prefill and decode stages of the LLM/SLM and heavily influenced by the underlying scheduling framework. The distinction between the prefill and decode stages, which dominate the inference LLM/SLM latency characteristics, is shown in Fig. 2.

Empirical evidence of tail latency in LLM serving. Recent measurement studies show that server-side LLM inference exhibits substantial tail-latency variation driven by request queuing, network delays, and shared-resource contention, rather than prompt length alone (Sun et al., 2025). Sun et al. decompose time-to-first-token (TTFT) into network, queueing, and prefill components and show that end-to-end latency variability persists even under controlled prompt distributions, highlighting why average throughput metrics are insufficient for time-sensitive applications (Sun et al., 2025).

Second, the reasoning time controlled by the agent flow, which may involve multiple, sequential/parallel or looped

LLM inference calls that follow an explicit or implicit thought pattern and that are scheduled by the underlying agentic framework. A simplified illustration of such an agentic flow, including interactions with tools and other agents, is presented in Fig. 3.

Third, the time delays introduced by external dependencies such as tool use, database queries, and inter-agent collaboration, which are heavily dependent on the scheduling and contention management for shared HW resources for compute and communication.

Figure 2. Illustration of the two main LLM inference stages: prefill and decode. Each stage is characterized by different and inference delays. 1) Prefill: Compute-bound and responsible for the time-to-first-token delay. In this stage the entire input prompt is processed and the resulting attention computations are cached. 2) Decode: Memory-bound and responsible for the delay between subsequent tokens. In this stage each newly generated token is processed by the attention heads while reusing cached computations from previous tokens.

To manage this complexity, a rich ecosystem of frameworks for each level has emerged. At the LLM inference level, scheduling techniques for batched and parallel inference requests have been proposed to optimize the use of HW resources for LLM inference like vLLM. vLLM includes the management of memory during the initial prefill stage (loading the input prompt), and the decode stage (generating tokens one by one).

At the agentic orchestration level, LangChain (LangChain, 2026a), LlamaIndex (Meta, 2026), Haystack (deepset, 2026), LangGraph (LangChain, 2026b), and AutoGen (Microsoft, 2026) are frameworks that have been proposed to control agentic flow execution and orchestration, for tool integration, and information retrieval, e.g., via Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) which enables to ground model outputs in factual knowledge. These tools focus on enabling the definition of multi-step chains in different implementations, such as dataflow pipes and event-based synchronization. However, they are not time-aware frameworks, i.e., the concept of time is not built-in, and thus it is not monitored nor controlled.

Concurrently, efforts are underway to standardize inter-agent interactions through agentic protocols for tool use and agent-to-agent communication (Yang et al., 2025), including

Figure 3. Simple agentic flow scenario to generate and execute an action with the use of tools and other agents. This scenario assumes no iterations, no corrections needed nor errors. Highlighted in pink are the steps that make use of generative AI (with unpredictable inference delay). Potential communication idle time is shown in white, where external components may too be based on generative AI.

the Model Context Protocol (MCP), Google’s A2A protocol, IBM’s Agent Communication Protocol (ACP) (IBM, 2026), and the Agent Network Protocol (ANP) (Chang, 2026), as surveyed in (Ehtesham et al., 2025). Similarly to agentic frameworks, these agentic protocols are not yet time-aware, and rather focus on enabling semantic communication of agent/tool capabilities and task descriptions.

2. Use Cases

Cyber-physical systems and agentic AI are converging in many environments in various markets. From traditional automation systems that incorporate agentic AI capabilities as new human-machine interface capabilities to new AI-driven decision making as part of the typical sensing-compute-actuation loop used by many autonomous systems. This section describes use cases where cyber-physical systems and agentic AI converge in the Isolation and Integration modalities. The use cases are not exhaustive but should be representative of a wide range of emerging applications that are driving the next generation cyber-physical systems augmented by agentic AI.

2.1. Real-Time workloads Isolated from Agentic AI

Consider a traditional factory automation use case where a Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) is used to control a given plant based on multiple sensory inputs. The plant may be a conveyor belt, for example, or other industrial machine/process. Many automation systems are transitioning to software-defined PLCs, where the PLC is running as a software workload on an Industrial computing device, aka soft-PLC, which also offers an interface (HMI) for operators to configure, interact and visualize data from the system. The HMI can be expected to incorporate agentic AI capabilities to enable new forms of interaction between the operator and the system. While the soft-PLC workload needs to meet strict latency and jitter requirements to ensure closing the control loop reliably/safely, the agentic AI workload needs to execute at the same time with good performance from a human interaction point of view. The agentic AI may be used at configuration stage (to receive instructions from

the operator) or during run time (collect data and provide information about the overall system performance). An example of this isolated mode convergence use case in a manufacturing environment is illustrated in Fig. 4.

Manufacturing
(Low-latency, Hard Real-time)

Figure 4. Isolation use case in manufacturing: Agentic AI enhances HMI interaction without impacting deterministic control

The isolated mode is prevalent in domains that can be enhanced from the added intelligence but at the same time need strict protection and guarantees for mission-critical systems. In novel contemporary systems, agentic AI serves as a high-level cognitive layer that coexists with, but must not interfere with, low-level deterministic control loops. The solutions needed for the isolation of the agentic AI and RT workloads in each of these applications is dependent on the specific timing and performance requirements which directly influence the architectures of the system, e.g., if what is processed locally, remotely and how to protect shared computation and communication resources.

For example, in **industrial robotics**, natural language is increasingly used for task and motion planning, allowing an operator to issue a high-level command that an AI breaks down into a sequence of fundamental robot tasks (Yu et al., 2026). The AI performs this cognitive work as a non-real-time task, often deployed at the cloud or local edge, while a separate real-time controller executes the resulting motion plan with deterministic precision. Similarly, **maintenance copilots** can analyze complex sensor data, consult technical manuals via RAG, and guide a technician through repairs, all while the machine’s safety-critical RTOS continues to operate without interruption.

This pattern extends to broader **manufacturing** scenarios, such as AI-based analytics for production optimization or the orchestration of AMR fleets, where high-level pathfind-

ing is AI-driven and low-level motor control is real-time. In **autonomous vehicles**, AI-based environmental perception is a cornerstone deployed locally, but it is architecturally segregated from the RT safety systems that manage braking and steering. Even on the shop floor, natural language agents can provide operational support to workers without impacting the deterministic PLCs that run the machinery. A representative example of such AI-driven orchestration while preserving RT guarantees is shown in Fig. 5.

AMR Orchestration

Figure 5. Isolation use case in retail: AI optimizes logistics and orchestrates AMRs, while RT workload ensures safe operation.

2.2. Real-Time Agentic AI Workloads

The more ambitious and challenging goal is to embed agentic AI directly into real-time loops such as perception, computation or control loops. These applications are categorized by the strictness of their deadlines.

Soft real-time applications, where missed deadlines degrade performance but are not catastrophic, are becoming feasible. Examples include algorithmic trading or real-time bidding, where an LLM-based agent strives for cost-effectiveness under tight deadlines (Cai et al., 2025). In manufacturing, this could involve AI systems that detect product defects or identify safety hazards, where timely but not perfectly deterministic responses are valuable.

Hard real-time applications, where a missed deadline constitutes a system failure, remain a formidable research challenge for agentic AI. A truly autonomous vehicle, or autonomous collaborating robots in human environments, where the end-to-end perception, planning, and action loop is handled by a single, integrated AI system that must meet hard deadlines is a long-term vision. More immediate ex-

amples include high-speed visual servoing, where an AI must identify, track, and guide a robot arm to manipulate an object on a fast-moving conveyor belt, requiring guaranteed response times to avoid failure. Fig. 6 illustrates this integration mode, where agentic AI operates as part of a continuous RT control loop with bounded latency.

Autonomous Driving

Figure 6. Integration use case: Agentic AI is embedded in a continuous, hard-RT control loop with bounded latency.

3. Core Challenges

The convergence of these disparate technological paradigms introduces profound challenges, which differ significantly depending on whether the goal is isolation or direct integration. The main categories of these challenges across application and platform layers are summarized in Fig. 7.

Figure 7. Broad challenge categories of integrating Agentic AI and RT workloads at the different system components. On the left, application-level challenges (red) are illustrated on both the generative AI component part (pink) and rule-based components. On the right, platform-level challenges (red), encompassing runtime frameworks, OS and HW resources necessary to run the agentic AI and RT workloads.

3.1. Challenges in Isolating Agentic AI

Achieving true, robust isolation on modern shared-hardware platforms is a non-trivial systems problem. Even worse, the resource-hungry nature of agentic AI creates both more

challenging direct and indirect interference paths.

Resource limitations are the most direct challenge. LLM workloads consume enormous GPU compute and memory bandwidth, which can starve co-located RT tasks.

Empirical studies quantify that even moderately sized LLMs impose substantial compute, memory, and energy demands relative to conventional deep learning workloads. For example, Tian et al. report that Llama-7B requires approximately 14 GB of memory for inference and incurs orders-of-magnitude higher energy per response than standard vision models, underscoring why co-locating LLM inference with time-critical workloads can induce system-level side effects (Tian et al., 2025).

More subtly, the large memory footprint of an LLM can pollute shared resources like the last-level cache, evicting critical data and instructions for an RT task and causing unpredictable execution time variations. This is further exacerbated in agentic AI, which orchestrates LLM inference calls with other tools. If the tools used are executed locally, they further contribute to the contention of CPU and memory resources.

Cross-domain resource contention, where the heavy, bursty execution of an AI workload can trigger system-wide effects like thermal throttling or DVFS. These mechanisms can lower the processor frequency for all cores, inadvertently slowing down an otherwise isolated RT task and jeopardizing its deadlines.

The real-time systems literature provides direct evidence that shared resources such as last-level caches, memory bandwidth, and thermal headroom can materially affect worst-case execution time and schedulability. Prior work demonstrates that cache interference and thermal coupling on heterogeneous CPU-GPU platforms introduce timing variability that must be explicitly managed to preserve real-time guarantees (Altmeyer et al., 2014; Hosseinimotlagh et al., 2019).

System-level risks. Agentic AIs that are empowered to call external APIs pierce the traditional trust boundaries of self-contained RT systems, introducing a potential vector for both security vulnerabilities and unpredictable network jitter.

Monitoring challenges. Finally, verifying that isolation is effective poses a significant challenge, requiring sophisticated observability tools to ensure RT metrics are met and to correctly attribute the root cause of any timing violations.

3.2. Challenges for Real-Time Agentic AI

Real-time agentic AI has to address the challenges described previously plus the following ones:

Inference temporal predictability gap Generative AI-based agentic systems are inherently probabilistic, adaptive, and data-dependent. The LLM/SLM auto-regressive generation process means *execution time* of a single inference call is not fixed. This conflict creates a significant temporal predictability gap. Worst-Case Execution Time (WCET) analysis, a cornerstone of real-time system verification, is currently intractable for generative AI. Its stochastic nature, combined with non-associativity of floating point operations in concurrent executions (Yuan et al., 2025), variability from complex hardware/software optimizations and resource contention in shared environments, makes static analysis of agentic AI with existing agentic frameworks and out-of-the-box foundational LLMs without explicit time-awareness nearly impossible.

Agentic flow temporal predictability gap There is an inherent trade-off between the quality and timeliness of a response; deeper reasoning may yield a better outcome but is likely to violate a deadline. The agentic work flow controls how often inference calls are made. Many current solutions allow the LLM model to implicitly define this workflow. Solutions where the workflow is explicitly defined, may contain loops and data-dependencies that makes timing analysis extremely difficult. Recent work on improving LLM robustness has shown that even purely model-level techniques increasingly rely on explicit multi-step inference pipelines, such as separating question interpretation from answer generation and ensembling over conditioned responses, which introduces additional sequential dependencies and variable execution paths that further complicate timing analysis (Rosales & Miret, 2025).

Decentralized intelligence in multi-agent systems The unpredictability of the agentic workflow is amplified in multi-agent systems, as a small delay in one agent can cascade through a collaborative workflow, leading to massive end-to-end jitter. Furthermore, this opens up new **security aspects**, as an adversary could craft inputs (e.g., via prompt injection) designed to maximize inference delay, effectively creating a denial-of-service attack on RT systems. Thus, input validation must evolve beyond sanitization to strict **complexity bounding**, ensuring that no input can trigger an unbounded reasoning chain that violates the temporal contract.

4. Existing Solutions and State-of-the-Art

In response to these challenges, the research and engineering communities have developed a range of solutions, with mature techniques for isolation and more nascent, best-effort approaches for real-time integration.

4.1. Solutions for Isolating Workloads

The state-of-the-art for isolating mixed-criticality workloads focuses on creating strong logical or physical partitions across the system stack. At the **compute platform** level, this involves a combination of software and hardware techniques. Real-Time Operating Systems (RTOS) provide deterministic scheduling and memory partitioning, while hypervisors offer stronger VM-level isolation. Modern SoCs are increasingly designed with mixed-criticality in mind, offering hardware features like Intel’s Time Coordinated Computing (TCC) (Intel, 2026), which includes Cache Allocation Technology (CAT), Memory Bandwidth Allocation (MBA), and cache locking. These tools allow system architects to reserve hardware resources exclusively for RT workloads. In parallel, specialized **LLM inference schedulers** are being developed to manage mixed SLO requirements, using techniques like request preemption and priority-aware batching to ensure that time-sensitive robotic queries, for example, are not delayed by best-effort analytical jobs (Borui et al., 2025; Ling et al., 2024; Zhang et al., 2025).

These compute strategies are complemented by solutions in the **communication stack**. Deterministic networking technologies like Time-Sensitive Networking (TSN) extend Ethernet to provide bounded latency and zero jitter for critical traffic flows. At the middleware layer, protocols like DDS provide rich QoS policies for deadline and liveness monitoring, enabling the robust integration of components with different timing requirements.

4.2. Solutions for Real-Time Agentic AI

This area is significantly less mature, with current solutions focusing on best-effort optimizations and architectural patterns rather than formal guarantees. A crucial first step has been to define appropriate **metrics for RT agentic applications** (Sagi, 2025), moving beyond simple tokens-per-second to throughput-oriented measures like Google’s GSU (Google, 2026) or multi-dimensional benchmarks that capture the trade-off between reasoning and resource usage (Li & Wang, 2025).

At the application level, a common **architectural practice** is to use hybrid deterministic-probabilistic agents, where the AI is responsible for high-level intent recognition and planning, while a separate deterministic module handles the time-critical execution. Research is also exploring how to create inherently **time-aware agents**. This includes dynamically verifying time-sensitive factual knowledge (Mousavi et al., 2024), injecting temporal information into model embeddings (Eldridge & Abdelshehid, 2025), and designing architectures for RT streaming tasks like speech recognition (Seide et al., 2024).

The bulk of current effort lies in best-effort optimization

techniques. Cloud providers offer specialized APIs (OpenAI, 2026) and provisioned throughput (e.g., Azure PTUs, Google GSUs) to guarantee a consistent level of performance by eliminating resource contention. At the model level, optimized LLM architectures are tailored for RT applications (Kannadasan, 2024). More advanced methods focus on adaptive prompting and reasoning, where the model’s “thinking time” is dynamically controlled to fit within a time budget, as surveyed in (Alomrani et al., 2025). This can be achieved via reinforcement learning to manage the length of reasoning chains (Xiang et al., 2025a;b; Team et al., 2025; Arora & Zanette, 2025) or by training models to recognize special tokens that prompt an early completion of their output (Aggarwal & Welleck, 2025; Muennighoff et al., 2025). Frameworks are also emerging to add runtime governance and monitoring controls to agentic systems (Wang et al., 2025).

5. Needed Future Solutions

Despite significant progress, fully and safely realizing the convergence of agentic AI and RT workloads requires overcoming fundamental research gaps.

5.1. For Isolated Workloads

The primary need is to validate component-level isolation solutions for effective, system-wide isolation of the new agentic workloads. Future work must focus on **validating integrated optimization frameworks** that co-design the AI planner, OS scheduler, and network fabric to provide holistic, end-to-end temporal guarantees. This must also account for subtle, indirect interference channels like thermal coupling. Furthermore, new methodologies for certification and assurance of agentic AI workloads are critical. **Formal methods and verifiable artifacts** are needed to prove that non-deterministic AI components (w.r.t. execution time), even when isolated, cannot under any circumstance compromise the safety properties of the real-time domain.

5.2. For Real-Time Agentic AI

Bridging the gap for integrated workloads requires a paradigm shift. First, we need **new timing models** that can reason about the probabilistic nature of AI designed for RT workloads. Research into probabilistic WCET (pWCET) frameworks and composable timing analyses is essential to formally bound AI latencies. Unlike traditional software, the challenge here lies in the vast parameter space and the state-dependent nature of auto-regressive generation. pWCET for LLMs must therefore move beyond statistical observation to active guidance, utilizing techniques like fine-tuning and in-context prompting to condition the model towards predictable stopping behaviors.

Second, this requires a **cross-layer co-design** approach to build time-awareness into the entire agentic stack. This vision includes:

- **Application-level:** Formalisms for specifying RT requirements.
- **Agent-level:** Real-time agentic frameworks that manage workflows against temporal contracts.
- **Orchestration-level:** Extensions to agentic protocols (e.g., MCP, A2A, ACP, ANP) to negotiate timing constraints for AI-tool and AI-AI collaboration.
- **Compute-level:** Real-time LLM inference serving that prioritizes predictability over raw throughput, acknowledging that deterministic execution may require “wasteful” resource reservation (e.g., disabling batching) to eliminate queuing delays.

Finally, beyond performance, agent reliability must be improved and not traded-off. Addressing the “reality gap” by developing robust planning, error detection, and self-correction mechanisms is crucial for deploying these systems in the real world, where both correctness and timeliness are paramount.

To concretize this abstract vision, consider a co-designed system where information flows vertically during a **setup phase** to align the stack before the real-time loop begins. The cycle starts when an *agentic protocol* (e.g., A2A, MCP) handshakes a strict timing budget derived from the application requirements. This budget flows down to the *orchestrator*, which locks the workflow using deterministic prompting templates and selects a *model* specifically optimized for the underlying hardware. The *inference engine* is then configured for deterministic scheduling, reserving strict *OS and hardware* partitions (e.g., cache locking). During the **runtime phase**, physical limits (like thermal headroom) established during setup act as hard constraints; if the agent approaches these limits, pre-negotiated fallback mechanisms are triggered instantly, rather than relying on slow, introspective reasoning. This separation of negotiation (setup) and execution (runtime) transforms independent components into a single, time-aware entity.

6. Falsifiable Claims and Success Criteria

To constitute a scientific contribution rather than a purely aspirational vision, the position advanced in this paper makes several falsifiable claims that can be evaluated by future research and deployments.

Claim 1: Isolation-only architectures will dominate safety-critical deployments unless time-aware agentic

stacks emerge. Absent explicit timing contracts and enforcement mechanisms across agentic frameworks, inference engines, and platforms, agentic AI will remain confined to isolated, advisory, or supervisory roles in real-time cyber-physical systems. This claim would be falsified by the demonstration of integrated agentic systems that operate within hard real-time control loops while providing verifiable bounds on end-to-end latency using existing, non-time-aware agentic frameworks.

Claim 2: Model-level architectural advances alone are insufficient to guarantee end-to-end timing predictability. Even if future model architectures reduce inference latency variance, system-level effects such as orchestration logic, tool invocation, shared-resource contention, and communication delays will continue to dominate worst-case behavior. This claim would be falsified by end-to-end systems in which bounded latency guarantees are achieved solely through model architecture choices, without cross-layer coordination or platform-level enforcement.

Claim 3: Real-time suitability of agentic AI cannot be assessed using accuracy or throughput metrics alone. For time-sensitive cyber-physical systems, metrics such as tail latency, deadline miss rate, and recovery behavior under overload are more indicative of system safety and reliability. This claim would be falsified if deployments demonstrate that accuracy-centric optimization reliably predicts safe operation despite significant timing variability.

Success Criteria. Progress toward validating or falsifying these claims can be measured through: (i) the existence of benchmarked agentic systems with explicit latency budgets, (ii) demonstrated composability of timing guarantees across agentic workflows, and (iii) certification or assurance artifacts that account for probabilistic execution behavior rather than assuming determinism.

7. Call to Action

To advance the safe and effective convergence of agentic AI and real-time systems, coordinated action across the machine learning, systems, and cyber-physical communities is required.

For the machine learning research community: Develop training objectives, evaluation protocols, and benchmarks that explicitly capture latency variance, tail behavior, and deadline adherence, rather than focusing solely on accuracy or average throughput.

For agentic framework developers: Incorporate explicit representations of time, deadlines, and execution budgets into agent orchestration frameworks, enabling workflows to be specified and monitored against temporal contracts.

For inference system designers: Explore inference-serving

modes that prioritize predictability over utilization efficiency, including deterministic scheduling, bounded batching, and resource reservation strategies appropriate for real-time contexts.

For protocol and middleware designers: Extend emerging agentic protocols to support the negotiation and enforcement of timing constraints for agent-to-agent and agent-to-tool interactions.

For systems and real-time researchers: Adapt and extend probabilistic timing analysis techniques to accommodate the scale, adaptivity, and state-dependent execution of generative and agentic AI workloads.

For standards bodies and certification stakeholders: Develop assurance frameworks and certification methodologies that explicitly acknowledge probabilistic execution behavior while still providing meaningful safety guarantees for mixed-criticality systems.

Collectively, these steps aim to shift real-time agentic AI from an ad hoc engineering challenge to a principled, measurable, and certifiable discipline.

8. Alternative Views

View 1: Agentic AI is Unnecessary for Integration. A fundamental skepticism exists regarding whether industrial and real-time workloads actually benefit from agentic capabilities. This view argues that traditional deterministic control theory (e.g., PID, MPC) and discriminative AI (computer vision) are already sufficient for high-performance automation. From this perspective, introducing nondeterministic, hallucination-prone agents into safety-critical loops adds immense complexity and risk without offering tangible value over existing, proven methodologies. *Response:* This overlooks the shifting requirements of modern automation, which demand flexibility and prediction over reactive repetition. While a PID controller excels at maintaining a setpoint, it cannot perform intelligent *predictive* decisions based on observed complex human behavior (e.g., anticipating a worker’s sudden movement based on their gaze or posture). The value of agentic AI lies in enabling systems to autonomously adapt and interact in these unstructured environments where simple state models fail.

View 2: Strict Hardware Isolation is Sufficient. A credible counter-position argues that the complexity of cross-layer co-design is unnecessary and that sufficient predictability can be achieved through strict hardware isolation and over-provisioning. Proponents of this view posit that advanced hardware partitions technologies (e.g., hypervisors, cache partitioning like Intel CAT, and dedicated NPUs) effectively decouple probabilistic AI workloads from deterministic real-time tasks. If the “fence” between domains

is strong enough, the AI’s internal non-determinism arguably becomes irrelevant to the safety-critical components. *Response:* While isolation improves safety, it does not solve the challenge of *integration*, where the AI itself must meet deadlines. Furthermore, even with strong partitioning, shared distinct resources like memory bandwidth and thermal headroom create indirect interference channels that can only be managed through system-level coordination.

View 3: Model Architecture Solves Latency. Another perspective suggests that the solution lies entirely within the AI domain, specifically in the development of new, inherently deterministic or bounded-time model architectures, rather than in system-level co-design. This view argues that the temporal unpredictability of current agentic AI systems is largely a consequence of autoregressive Transformer-based generation, and that future architectures, such as State Space Models (SSMs), non-autoregressive generation, or diffusion-based language models, will fundamentally eliminate the temporal predictability gap at the source.

Response: While advances in model architecture may reduce certain sources of latency variance, they are insufficient to guarantee end-to-end timing predictability in real-time cyber-physical systems. In particular, diffusion-based language models, which generate outputs through iterative denoising rather than token-by-token autoregression, are often cited as a promising path toward bounded inference time. In practice, however, the number of diffusion steps required to reach task-dependent correctness or quality thresholds is itself data- and context-dependent, and is frequently adapted dynamically to trade solution quality for latency. Mechanisms such as early stopping, adaptive step schedules, guidance strength, and conditioning complexity reintroduce variability in the effective iteration count. Moreover, even if a strict upper bound on model-level inference steps were enforced, end-to-end latency in agentic systems would remain dominated by system-level factors, including orchestration logic, tool invocation, multi-agent coordination, communication delays, and shared-resource contention. Consequently, architectural innovations alone, whether autoregressive, non-autoregressive, or diffusion-based, cannot ensure real-time suitability without cross-layer coordination and explicit time awareness across the agentic stack.

References

- Aggarwal, P. and Welleck, S. L1: Controlling how long a reasoning model thinks with reinforcement learning, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2503.04697>.
- Alomrani, M. A., Zhang, Y., Li, D., Sun, Q., Pal, S., Zhang, Z., Hu, Y., Ajwani, R. D., Valkanas, A., Karimi, R., Cheng, P., Wang, Y., Liao, P., Huang, H., Wang, B., Hao, J., and Coates, M. Reasoning on a budget: A survey of adaptive and controllable test-time compute in LLMs, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.02076>.
- Altmeyer, S., Douma, R., Lunniss, W., and Davis, R. I. Evaluation of cache partitioning for hard real-time systems. In *26th Euromicro Conference on Real-Time Systems, ECRTS 2014, Madrid, Spain, July 8-11, 2014*, pp. 15–26. IEEE Computer Society, 2014. doi: 10.1109/ECRTS.2014.11. URL <https://doi.org/10.1109/ECRTS.2014.11>.
- Arora, D. and Zanette, A. Training language models to reason efficiently, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2502.04463>.
- Borui, W., Juntao, Z., Chenyu, J., Chuanxiong, G., and Chuan, W. Efficient llm serving on hybrid real-time and best-effort requests, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.09590>.
- Cai, L., He, J., Li, Y., Liang, J., Lin, Y., Quan, Z., Zeng, Y., and Xu, J. RTBAgent: A LLM-based agent system for real-time bidding. In *Companion Proceedings of the ACM on Web Conference 2025, WWW ’25*, pp. 104–113, New York, NY, USA, 2025. Association for Computing Machinery. ISBN 9798400713316. doi: 10.1145/3701716.3715259. URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3701716.3715259>.
- Chang, G. Agent Network Protocol. <https://www.agent-network-protocol.com/specs/white-paper>, 2026. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- deepset. Haystack. <https://haystack.deepset.ai/>, 2026. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- Ehtesham, A., Singh, A., Gupta, G. K., and Kumar, S. A survey of agent interoperability protocols: Model context protocol (MCP), agent communication protocol (ACP), agent-to-agent protocol (A2A), and agent network protocol (ANP), 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2505.02279>.
- Eldridge, L. J. and Abdelshehid, E. S. Time-injected large language models: A novel technique for producing agent behavior. June 2025. doi: 10.36227/techrxiv.175037127.71250235/v1. URL <http://dx.doi.org/10.36227/techrxiv.175037127.71250235/v1>.
- Google. GSU. <https://cloud.google.com/vertex-ai/generative-ai/docs/provisioned-throughput/measure-provisioned-throughput>, 2026. Accessed: 2026-01-23.

- Hosseinimotlagh, S. A., Guo, Y., Eker, J., and Eles, P. Thermal-aware scheduling of real-time tasks on CPU-GPU heterogeneous platforms. In *Proceedings of the 31st Euromicro Conference on Real-Time Systems (ECRTS)*, 2019.
- IBM. Agent Communication Protocol. <https://agentcommunicationprotocol.dev>, 2026. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- Intel. Time Coordinated Computing. <https://www.intel.com/content/www/us/en/content-details/747345/intel-time-coordinated-computing-intel-tcc.html>, 2026. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- Kannadasan, T. Optimizing LLM architectures for real-time applications in full-stack development. In *2024 3rd International Conference on Automation, Computing and Renewable Systems (ICACRS)*, pp. 721–726, 2024. doi: 10.1109/ICACRS62842.2024.10841540. URL <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10841540>.
- Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., and Hinton, G. E. Imagenet classification with deep convolutional neural networks. *Commun. ACM*, 60(6):84–90, 2017. doi: 10.1145/3065386. URL <https://doi.org/10.1145/3065386>.
- LangChain. LangChain. <https://www.langchain.com/>, 2026a. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- LangChain. LangGraph. <https://www.langchain.com/langgraph>, 2026b. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- Li, Z. and Wang, S. Reasoning as a resource: Optimizing fast and slow thinking in code generation models, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.09396>.
- Liang, B.-S. AI compute architecture and evolution trends, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.21394>.
- Ling, N., Chen, G., and Zhong, L. TimelyLLM: Segmented llm serving system for time-sensitive robotic applications, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2412.18695>.
- Machines, T. Defeating Nondeterminism in LLM Inference. <https://thinkingmachines.ai/blog/defeating-nondeterminism-in-llm-inference/>, 2026. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- Meta. LlamaIndex. <https://www.llamaindex.ai/>, 2026. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- Microsoft. AutoGen. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/autogen/>, 2026. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- Mnih, V., Kavukcuoglu, K., Silver, D., Rusu, A. A., Veness, J., Bellemare, M. G., Graves, A., Riedmiller, M., Fidjeland, A. K., Ostrovski, G., et al. Human-level control through deep reinforcement learning. *nature*, 518(7540): 529–533, 2015. URL <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature14236>.
- Mousavi, S. M., Alghisi, S., and Riccardi, G. DyKnow: Dynamically verifying time-sensitive factual knowledge in LLMs. In Al-Onaizan, Y., Bansal, M., and Chen, Y. (eds.), *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2024, Miami, Florida, USA, November 12-16, 2024*, pp. 8014–8029. Association for Computational Linguistics, 2024. doi: 10.18653/v1/2024.FINDINGS-EMNLP.471. URL <https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2024.findings-emnlp.471>.
- Muennighoff, N., Yang, Z., Shi, W., Li, X. L., Fei-Fei, L., Hajishirzi, H., Zettlemoyer, L., Liang, P., Candès, E., and Hashimoto, T. sl: Simple test-time scaling, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.19393>.
- OpenAI. Realtime API. <https://platform.openai.com/docs/guides/realtime>, 2026. Accessed: 2026-01-23.
- Rosales, R. and Miret, S. Diverse LLMs or diverse question interpretations? that is the ensembling question, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2507.21168>.
- Sagi, S. Optimizing LLM inference: Metrics that matter for real time applications. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence & Cloud Computing*, pp. 1–4, 02 2025. doi: 10.47363/JAICC/2025(4)446.
- Schick, T., Dwivedi-Yu, J., Dessi, R., Raileanu, R., Lomeli, M., Hambro, E., Zettlemoyer, L., Cancedda, N., and Scialom, T. Toolformer: Language models can teach themselves to use tools. In Oh, A., Naumann, T., Globerson, A., Saenko, K., Hardt, M., and Levine, S. (eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 36: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2023, NeurIPS 2023, New Orleans, LA, USA, December 10 - 16, 2023*, 2023. URL http://papers.nips.cc/paper_files/paper/2023/hash/d842425e4bf79ba039352da0f658a906-Abstract-Conference.html.
- Seide, F., Doulaty, M., Shi, Y., Gaur, Y., Jia, J., and Wu, C. Speech ReaLLM – real-time streaming speech recognition with multimodal LLMs by teaching the flow of time, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.09569>.
- Shortliffe, E. H. and Buchanan, B. G. A model of inexact reasoning in medicine. *Mathematical Biosciences*, 23(3):351–379, 1975. ISSN 0025-5564. doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5564\(75\)90016-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/0025-5564(75)90016-1).

- i.org/10.1016/0025-5564(75)90047-4. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0025556475900474>.
- Sun, T., Wang, P., and Lai, F. DiSCo: Device-server collaborative LLM-based text streaming services. In Che, W., Nabende, J., Shutova, E., and Pilehvar, M. T. (eds.), *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics, ACL 2025, Vienna, Austria, July 27 - August 1, 2025*, pp. 14259–14277. Association for Computational Linguistics, 2025. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2025.findings-acl.734/>.
- Sutton, R. S., Precup, D., and Singh, S. Between MDPs and semi-MDPs: A framework for temporal abstraction in reinforcement learning. *Artificial Intelligence*, 112(1): 181–211, 1999. ISSN 0004-3702. doi: 10.1016/S0004-3702(99)00052-1. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0004370299000521>.
- Team, K., Du, A., Gao, B., Xing, B., Jiang, C., Chen, C., Li, C., Xiao, C., Du, C., Liao, C., Tang, C., Wang, C., Zhang, D., Yuan, E., Lu, E., Tang, F., Sung, F., Wei, G., Lai, G., Guo, H., Zhu, H., Ding, H., Hu, H., Yang, H., Zhang, H., Yao, H., Zhao, H., Lu, H., Li, H., Yu, H., Gao, H., Zheng, H., Yuan, H., Chen, J., Guo, J., Su, J., Wang, J., Zhao, J., Zhang, J., Liu, J., Yan, J., Wu, J., Shi, L., Ye, L., Yu, L., Dong, M., Zhang, N., Ma, N., Pan, Q., Gong, Q., Liu, S., Ma, S., Wei, S., Cao, S., Huang, S., Jiang, T., Gao, W., Xiong, W., He, W., Huang, W., Xu, W., Wu, W., He, W., Wei, X., Jia, X., Wu, X., Xu, X., Zu, X., Zhou, X., Pan, X., Charles, Y., Li, Y., Hu, Y., Liu, Y., Chen, Y., Wang, Y., Liu, Y., Qin, Y., Liu, Y., Yang, Y., Bao, Y., Du, Y., Wu, Y., Wang, Y., Zhou, Z., Wang, Z., Li, Z., Zhu, Z., Zhang, Z., Wang, Z., Yang, Z., Huang, Z., Huang, Z., Xu, Z., Yang, Z., and Lin, Z. Kimi k1.5: Scaling reinforcement learning with LLMs, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.12599>.
- Tian, C., Qin, X., Tam, K., Li, L., Wang, Z., Zhao, Y., Zhang, M., and Xu, C. CLONE: customizing LLMs for efficient latency-aware inference at the edge. In Altinbüken, D. and Stutsman, R. (eds.), *Proceedings of the 2025 USENIX Annual Technical Conference, USENIX ATC 2025, Boston, MA, USA, July 7-9, 2025*, pp. 563–585. USENIX Association, 2025. URL <https://www.usenix.org/conference/atc25/presentation/tian>.
- Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., Kaiser, L., and Polosukhin, I. Attention is all you need. In Guyon, I., von Luxburg, U., Bengio, S., Wallach, H. M., Fergus, R., Vishwanathan, S. V. N., and Garnett, R. (eds.), *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 30: Annual Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems 2017, December 4-9, 2017, Long Beach, CA, USA*, pp. 5998–6008, 2017. URL <https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2017/hash/3f5ee243547dee91fbd053c1c4a845aa-Abstract.html>.
- Wang, C. L., Singhal, T., Kelkar, A., and Tuo, J. MI9 – agent intelligence protocol: Runtime governance for agentic AI systems, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2508.03858>.
- Xiang, V., Blagden, C., Rafailov, R., Lile, N., Truong, S., Finn, C., and Haber, N. Just enough thinking: Efficient reasoning with adaptive length penalties reinforcement learning, 2025a. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.05256>.
- Xiang, V., Snell, C., Gandhi, K., Albalak, A., Singh, A., Blagden, C., Phung, D., Rafailov, R., Lile, N., Mahan, D., Castricato, L., Franken, J.-P., Haber, N., and Finn, C. Towards system 2 reasoning in LLMs: Learning how to think with meta chain-of-thought, 2025b. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.04682>.
- Yang, Y., Chai, H., Song, Y., Qi, S., Wen, M., Li, N., Liao, J., Hu, H., Lin, J., Chang, G., Liu, W., Wen, Y., Yu, Y., and Zhang, W. A survey of AI agent protocols, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.16736>.
- Yao, S., Zhao, J., Yu, D., Du, N., Shafran, I., Narasimhan, K. R., and Cao, Y. ReAct: Synergizing reasoning and acting in language models. In *The Eleventh International Conference on Learning Representations, ICLR 2023, Kigali, Rwanda, May 1-5, 2023*. OpenReview.net, 2023. URL https://openreview.net/forum?id=WE_vluYUL-X.
- Yu, Z., Zhang, P., and Shi, J. Transformation of industrial robotics with natural language models: Recent progress and future prospects. *Robotics and Computer-Integrated Manufacturing*, 97:103113, 2026. ISSN 0736-5845. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcim.2025.103113>. URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S073658452500167X>.
- Yuan, J., Li, H., Ding, X., Xie, W., Li, Y.-J., Zhao, W., Wan, K., Shi, J., Hu, X., and Liu, Z. Understanding and mitigating numerical sources of nondeterminism in LLM inference, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2506.09501>.
- Zhang, W., Wu, Z., Mu, Y., Ning, R., Liu, B., Sarda, N., Lee, M., and Lai, F. JITServe: SLO-aware LLM serving with imprecise request information, 2025. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.20068>.